

SZ-HB-II-02-08 Search for a course at another university (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261291
ID	SZ-HB-II-02-08
Title	Search for a course at another university
Educational area	#higher-education
Persona	P: Nadine - Student https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951710
Short description	Nadine is interested in a course offered at another university.
Result	Nadine finds a course that suits her needs at another university.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Search for a course at another university"• Part 2: "Contacting a lecturer at another university"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Nadine is registered at BIRD.• Nadine is logged in to BIRD
Components	#learningpathfinder #profile #contacts
Services / tools	#STUD-IP

Problem scenario

Introduction

Nadine Kasoevi is studying Education and Mathematics at the University of Vechta. She is in her eighth semester and would like to take an additional course in Environmental Sciences on a voluntary basis before completing her bachelor's degree. Since her university does not offer courses in this field, she would like to find out about courses offered by other universities, preferably in German-speaking countries. If possible, she would like to register as a guest student for a suitable course and, gain access to the course materials so that she can work on them from Vechta.

Problem definition

Nadine is interested in the interactions between humans and nature as well as events with an environmental science focus. She enjoys taking courses that are not explicitly

part of her curriculum and values learning about new topics or exploring them in greater depth. At the time of her search, her own university does not offer any courses that spark her interest. She therefore wants to look into how guest student status at another university work and what steps are required to obtain it. Nadine would like to be able to get an overview of the courses available at other universities and register easily and without complications.

Background and context

Nadine is about to complete her bachelor's degree and plans to continue her studies immediately afterwards. She is not yet sure which master's program or university are the right choice for her. Nadine is willing to take an additional course at another university to find out whether a master's degree with a focus on environmental sciences would be suitable for her. She is open to attending a course in person, online or in a hybrid format, but only if the enrollment and participation do not require too much of an additional effort. She would also appreciate to have the course credited towards her master's degree, but this is not her top priority.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Searching for courses online feels ineffective and frustrating to Nadine, as it takes a lot of time to gather necessary information from university websites. This applies both to selecting and comparing different courses and their contents as well as to understanding the formal requirements for participation or guest enrollment. These factors vary from university to university.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Nadine searched for courses using online search engines but did not find anything immediately. It is very frustrating for Nadine to search through the course catalogs and examination regulations of individual universities for relevant information. These are usually only available as PDF files and therefore cannot be searched using standard search engines. In order to obtain further information and possibly make contacts, Nadine asked a biology lecturer at the University of Vechta, for recommendations in the field of environmental sciences. However, she was unable to obtain any helpful information or make any contacts from this conversation.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Search for a course at another university"

Step 1: Nadine logs into BIRD. Her goal is to explore courses offered at universities near Vechta and to find a course that suits her interests.

Step 2: Nadine opens the LearningPathFinder and enters the following keywords in the search field: "university course for external students", "guest student status", "biology" and "environmental sciences".

Step 3: The system displays seminars at several universities. Since Nadine prefers local courses, she applies a filter to show results within 50 km radius of Vcheta.

Step 4: In the refined list of results, Nadine notices the course "*Human-Environment Interactions*" in the Environmental Sciences program at the University of Oldenburg.

Step 5: She clicks on the course entry. The LearningPathFinder shows her a summary along with the relevant examination regulations provided by the University of Oldenburg in the BIRD data room.

Step 6: Nadine saves the course to her favorites and decides to contact the person in charge in the next few days to find out whether she can take this course as a guest student and if so, whether she will have access the course material.

Part 2: "Contacting a lecturer at another university"

Step 1: Nadine logs in to BIRD.

Step 2: Nadine opens her saved favorites in the LearningPathFinder. There she clicks on the course *Human-Environment Interaction* at the University of Oldenburg, which opens its information page.

Step 3: In the course information, she finds the name of lecturer XY. She copies it into the global search in BIRD and adds the university, course title, and degree program. The system displays the lecturer's contact details as a digital business card.

Step 4: Nadine opens the lecturer's business card. She sends a contact request and then writes a direct message introducing herself briefly and asking whether she can participate in the course.

Step 5: A few days later, Nadine receives a reply from the lecturer at the University of Oldenburg. She informs Nadine that she can enroll as a guest student.

Step 6: Nadine visits the section for guest students on the University of Oldenburg website ([your path to becoming a guest student](#)). She follows the instructions to register as a guest student and obtain her own account in the Stud.IP system at the University of Oldenburg. *

Step 7: Nadine logs out of BIRD and waits for confirmation from the University of Oldenburg as well as the activation of her Stud.IP account.

* As of April 2025, the University of Oldenburg and the University of Vechta do not have an official cooperation agreement. This may mean that academic credits cannot be accredited.